

Highly-efficient Ho:KY(WO₄)₂ thin-disk lasers at 2.06 μm

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OUTLINE

*Motivation and introduction. The **monoclinic double tungstates***

*Fabrication of the **thin-disk** structures*

*Spectroscopy of the **Ho** ions*

*Laser setup for the **Ho thin-disk** laser*

CW and Q-switched laser operation

Conclusion and future work

MOTIVATION

State of the art: Tm-based thin-disk lasers

500 μm thick, 10 at.% Tm:YAG: up to 2 W ($T = -30^\circ \text{C}$), *A. Dienes et al., CLEO'98.*

650 μm thick, 6 at.% Tm:YAG: up to 4 W ($T = -17^\circ \text{C}$), *N. Berner et al., ASSL'99.*

- 4 bounces of the pump (8 pump passes)

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200-500 μm thick, 5 at.% Tm:Lu₂O₃: 0.5 W, *M. Schellhorn et al., ASSP, ATuB14 (2011).*

- 12 bounces of the pump

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250 μm thick, 12 at.% Tm:LLF: 21 W @ 1910 nm, *G. Stoeppler et al., Opt. Lett. 37, 1163 (2012).*

-12 bounces of the pump

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300 μm thick, 4 at.% Tm:YAG: 24 W @ 2014 nm,

J. Zhang et al., Laser & Photon. Rev. 12, 1700273 (2018).

-36 bounces of the pump

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Vey complex pump scheme

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State of the art: Ho-based thin-disk lasers

400 μm , 2 at.% Ho:YAG: 9.4 W @ 2090 nm, slope $\eta \sim 50\%$, pumped by a Tm:YLF laser,
M. Schellhorn, Appl. Phys. B85, 549 (2006)

- 12 bounces of the pump (typical for YAG thin-disks), limited Ho-concentration because of upconversion losses;

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400 μm , 2 at.% Ho:YAG: 15 W @ 2090 nm, pumped by a Tm: fiber laser,
J. Speiser et al., SPIE 7912, 79120C (2011) and *Proc. of SPIE 8547, 85470E-1-11 (2012)*

- 12 bounces of the pump, limited Ho-concentration.
- 22 W with $\eta \sim 26\%$, in a similar 2.5 at. % Ho:YAG laser pumped by an InP diode,
G. Renz, Proc. of SPIE 9342, 93421W (2015).

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200 μm , 2.5 at.% Ho:YAG: 50 W @ 2091/2097 nm, pumped by a Tm: fiber laser,

- 36 bounces of the pump,

J. Zhang et al., Laser & Photon. Rev. 12, 1700273 (2018).

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GENERAL OBJECTIVE

Our aim was to develop a **Ho thin-disk** laser with
simplified pump geometry based on the **monoclinic**
double tungstate crystals

INTRODUCTION

Monoclinic double tungstates

Substituted ions:

Y^{3+} , Gd^{3+} , Lu^{3+}

Trivalent active ions:

Yb^{3+} , Tm^{3+} , Er^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Ho^{3+}

Structural and thermal properties

**High doping levels for the active ions
(up to 5% for Ho-doping)**

Moderate thermal conductivity

"Athermal" thermo-optic behaviour

example: *KLuW* crystal

Ln^{3+} spectroscopic properties

Large transition cross-sections

Broad absorption and emission bands

Weak concentration-quenching

Strong Raman activity

V. Petrov et al., Laser & Photon. Rev. 1, 179 (2007).

INTRODUCTION

- ⇒ Ideally suited for the-thin disk laser concept
- ⇒ Disk thickness $< 100 \mu\text{m}$ sufficient absorption.
- ⇒ Epitaxial structures required
- ⇒ Single bounce pumping possible: compared to typically ~ 12 bounces of the pump used (24 pump passes).
- ⇒ Reduced complexity of the pump geometry

Thin-Disk laser based on $50 \mu\text{m}$ Yb(32%):KLuW epitaxy

S. Rivier et al., Opt. Lett. 33, 735 (2008).

INTRODUCTION

Thin-Disk laser based on 250 μm
Tm(5%):KLuW epitaxy

S. Vatik et al., Opt. Lett. 37, 356 (2012).

Output coupler:

$T_{OC} = 4\%$, $R_{OC} = -40$ mm.

$\eta = 47\%$ (vs. absorbed power)

Pump laser light: horizontally polarized, $E // N_m$

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FABRICATION of the THIN DISK STRUCTURES

MDT substrates.

Top-Seeded Solution Growth (TSSG) method.
Oriented normal to the *b*-axis.
1 – 1.5 mm-thick.

Epitaxies.

Liquid Phase Epitaxy (LPE) method

FABRICATION of the THIN DISK STRUCTURES

SPECTROSCOPY of Ho^{3+} in MDT CRYSTALS

Lifetime ($5I_7$): ~ 4.2 ms

Higher gain for $E \parallel N_m$

Absorption and emission cross-section of **Ho:KYW**. $5I_7 \leftrightarrow 5I_8$ transition near 2000 nm.
Light polarization $E \parallel N_m$

LASER SETUP for the *Ho:KYW* THIN-DISK

Pump source: Tm fiber laser
(Model IFL15, LISA laser products, OHG)
emitting up to 12.5 W at 1960 nm (FWHM = 1.5
nm), unpolarized output with $M^2 \sim 1$.

LASER RESULTS – quasi-CW mode (1:2, 20 Hz)

The 3 at. % Ho:KYW laser generated a peak power of **1.10 W** at 2056-2059 nm, $\eta = 66\%$

The 5 at. % Ho:KYW laser provided an increased output power of **1.31 W** (higher absorption) at 2057-2059 and 2072-2075 nm albeit at reduced slope efficiency, $\eta = 34\%$.

Pump absorption, single bounce:

3at.% Ho, Abs = 14%, **5at.% Ho**, Abs = 33%

Stronger thermo-optic aberrations and higher upconversion losses associated with stronger heat load at higher **Ho³⁺** doping.

Neither fracture of the disk nor thermal roll-over of the output dependence were observed up to at least $P_{\text{abs}} = 4.20$ W.

LASER RESULTS – CW mode

Agreement with the gain spectra
(recorded at $P_{abs} = 1.52$ W, single bounce)

CW mode: more pronounced difference in the output performance

The 3 at. % Ho:KYW laser generated **1.01 W** with $\eta = 60\%$ whereas the maximum output from the 5 at. % Ho:KYW laser was only **0.24 W** with $\eta = 15\%$.

The effect of **Ho³⁺** concentration is due to the increasing reabsorption losses.

LASER RESULTS

Comparison of the output performance of the **Ho:KYW** thin-disk laser in CW and quasi-CW operation modes for 1 and 2 bounces of the pump, $T_{OC} = 3\%$.

Worse mode matching produced lower η and higher threshold.

Pump absorption: 1 bounce **14%**, 2 bounces **25%**

LASER RESULTS – Q-switched regime

Max. average output power: 0.51 W @ 2056.3 nm ($\eta = 44\%$)
 Q-switching conversion efficiency with respect to CW: **93%**

Intensity instabilities: $< 10\%$
 rms pulse-to-pulse timing jitter: $< 7\%$

LASER RESULTS – thermo-optic effects

Spatial profiles measured at different P_{abs} (CW, $T_{\text{OC}} = 1.5\%$). Astigmatism of the thermal lens $M^2_x = 3.1$ $M^2_y = 1.6$

Spatial profiles of the output laser beam measured at (a) low $P_{\text{abs}} = 0.39$ W and (b) high $P_{\text{abs}} = 1.78$ W (CW, single bounce of the pump, $T_{\text{OC}} = 3\%$).

A and B – major and minor semiaxes of the elliptic laser beam;
 X'_1 and X'_3 – principal axes of the thermal expansion tensor of KYW.

LASER RESULTS – thermo-optic effects

For the 3 at. % **Ho:KYW** thin-disk laser: purely negative (defocusing) lens.

Sensitivity factors ($M = dD/dP_{\text{abs}}$): $M_x = -1.7$, $M_y = -0.6 \text{ m}^{-1}/\text{W}$.

Related to negative thermo-optic coefficient of **KYW** at $\sim 2 \mu\text{m}$, $dn_m/dT = -8.9 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$, and suppression of the positive effect of end-bulging by the substrate / undoped cap.

Upconversion luminescence (UCL): reveals excited state processes vs. doping

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

1- A CW **Ho:KYW/KYW** thin-disk laser generated 1.01 W (~1.6 W) at 2056-2059 nm with a slope efficiency η of 60% (55%) for a single (**double**) bounce of the pump at 1960 nm: promising also for compact Q-switched or mode-locked thin-disk lasers of this type.

2- The spectroscopy of the **Ho** ion indicates good suitability of the **Ho:KYW/KYW** epitaxy for thin-disk lasers; while thermo-optic effects, related to doping level, might be an issue.

In future:

We plan to optimize the **Ho** concentration (1-3 at.%), compare with multi-pass pumping, increase the pump spot size for power scaling, and test readjusted pump polarization for the 2nd pass or other crystal orientations (N_g -cut).

Thank you for your attention

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